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AN EXPLORATORY STUDY ON WOMEN'S PERCEPTION TOWARDS BOUTIQUE SHOPS IN PALAYAMKOTTAI

A. Benazir ¹

Dr. M. Sulthana Barvin ²

Abstract

Customer perception refers to the process by which a customer selects, organizes and interprets information to create a meaningful picture of a brand or a product. If a customer is satisfied that means that a product or service has met his expectations. Customer satisfaction is doubtlessly very important, and it leads to repeat purchases. This study focuses on women's perception towards boutique shops in Palayamkottai area. A boutique is a small store that sells stylish clothing, jewellery and other luxury goods. Boutiques remain a vital part of commercial world of fashion. This research work gives a broad framework of women's perception towards boutique shops in Palayamkottai area. The researcher covers five boutique shops in Palayamkottai. The study is a descriptive survey study. Primary data is collected through self-structured questionnaire. Well-structured questionnaire is distributed to 100 respondents and collected back only 96 questionnaires and among that 2 questionnaires were inadequate data. So the sample size is restricted to 94. Secondary data is collected from existing reports, books, journals & magazines and websites. The sample size of the study was 94 respondents and they were selected from Palayamkottai according to the convenience. Statistical tools like percentage analysis, weighted score, Garrett ranking method and chi square were used.

Keywords: Boutique shop, perception, factors influencing, physical facilities

Introduction

Customer perception refers to the process by which a customer selects, organizes and interprets information to create a meaningful picture of a brand or a product. If a customer is satisfied that means that a product or service has met his expectations. Customer satisfaction is doubtlessly very important, and it leads to repeat purchases. A loyal customer however is more than a customer who frequently purchases, and they truly prefer a product, brand or company over competitive offerings. This study focuses on women's perception towards boutique shops in Palayamkottai area. A boutique is a small store that sells stylish clothing, jewelry and other luxury goods. Boutiques remain a vital part of commercial world of fashion. This research work gives a broad framework of women's perception towards boutique shops in Palayamkottai area. The researcher covers five boutique shops in Palayamkottai namely Shivane's boutique, Shree fashion boutiques, Prabhas boutiques, Ria's boutique and Zarah's boutique. This study has been conducted in Palayamkottai covering all the areas with a sample of 94 respondents.

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Review of literature

Review of related literature is an important step in undertaking research. It helps in clarifying and defining the problem, stating objectives, formulating hypotheses, selecting appropriate design and methodology of research as well as interpreting the results in the light of the research work already undertaken. **Reham Abdelbaset Sanad (2016)** This paper aims to make a comprehensive review of factors affecting purchaser decision towards apparel. It is believed that textile product's visual and physical characteristics has a great impact on consumer buying decision.

Deepali Saluja (2016) This study shows that the age, gender, education and occupation do not have any impact on buying behaviour of consumers. Finally, the survey shows that Delhi consumers have positive attitude towards fashion apparel brands.

Objectives of the study

1. To understand the perception of women towards the boutique shops in Palayamkottai area
2. To identify the factors influencing the women towards the boutique shop
3. To find out the reasons for choosing a boutique shop
4. To analyse the customer perception towards service quality of boutique shop

Research design

- The study is a descriptive survey study.
- Primary data is collected through self-structured questionnaire. Well-structured questionnaire is distributed to 100 respondents and collected back only 96 questionnaires and among that 2 questionnaires were inadequate data. So, the sample size is restricted to 94.
- Secondary data is collected from existing reports, books, journals & magazines and websites.
- The sample size of the study was 94 respondents and they were selected from Palayamkottai according to the convenience.
- Statistical tools like percentage analysis, weighted score, Garrett ranking method and chi square were used.

Data presentation, analysis & interpretation

Table 1: Demographic Profile of the respondents

Variables	Particulars	Frequency	Percentage
Age	Below 20	10	11%
	21-30	16	19%
	31-40	21	22%
	41- 50	31	33%
	51 – 60	10	11%
	Above 60	04	04%
Educational Qualification	School level	30	32%
	College level	52	55%
	Others	12	13%

Variables	Particulars	Frequency	Percentage
Occupation	Student	20	21%
	Government employee	17	18%
	Private employee	24	26%
	Professional	14	15%
	Others	19	20%
Marital Status	Married	60	64%
	Unmarried	34	36%
Monthly income	Below ₹ 30,000	57	61%
	₹ 30,000- ₹ 50,000	24	25%
	above ₹ 50,000	13	14%
Nature of family	Joint family	29	31%
	Nuclear family	65	69%
Size of the family	upto 2 members	7	7%
	2-4 members	57	61%
	4-6 members	22	23%
	Above 6 members	8	9%

Source: Primary Data

Majority (33%) of our respondents are between the age group of 41-50 year; Majority (55%) of the respondents have completed college level; Majority (26%) of our respondents are private employees; Majority (64%) of the respondents are married; Majority (61%) of the respondents have the monthly income of below 30000; Majority (69 %) of the respondents live in nuclear family and they have 2 -4 members in their family.

Table 2: Respondent's perception towards boutique shop

Variables	Particulars	Frequency	Percentage
Frequency of purchase	Two Week once	6	6%
	Monthly once	22	23%
	Once in Six months	17	18%
	Once in a year	25	27%
	Rarely	24	26%
Time spend for purchasing	Less than 1 hour	17	18%
	1 to 3 hours	41	44%
	More than 3 hours	36	38%
Buying preference	Online boutique	21	22%
	Boutique shop	42	45%
	Both	31	33%
Preference of dresses in boutique shop	Traditional wear	46	49%
	Modern wear	16	17%
	Both	32	34%
Amount spend on single purchase	₹ 1000	16	17%
	₹ 1001 to ₹ 5000	49	52%
	₹ 5000 to ₹ 10000	19	20%
	Above ₹ 10000	10	11%

Variables	Particulars	Frequency	Percentage
Perception towards physical facility	Interiors is appealing	30	32%
	Good image	20	21%
	Environmental consciousness	27	29%
	Good lightning	6	6%
	Locations	11	12%

Source: Primary Data

Majority of the respondents say that they purchase from boutique shop once in a year; Majority of the respondents says that they take 1 - 5 hours to purchase a dress; Majority of the respondents prefer to buy from boutique shop than online boutique and they prefer only traditional wear; Majority of the respondents spend nearly Rs1000 to Rs 5000 for a single purchase and Majority of the respondents say that interior is appealing in boutique shop.

Table 3: Respondents perception towards boutique shops

Likert scaling method is used to analyze the respondent's perception towards Boutique shop.

Statement	Strongly agree (5)	Agree (4)	Neutral (3)	Disagree (2)	Strongly Disagree (1)	Total score	Average Score	Rank
Prices are advantages	12 (60)	15 (60)	12 (36)	23 (46)	32 (32)	234	46.8	IV
Products are of high quality	32 (160)	23 (92)	12 (36)	12 (24)	15 (15)	327	65.4	I
Sales personnel is professional	15 (75)	20 (80)	14 (42)	17 (34)	28 (28)	259	51.8	III
Sales personnel is friendly	12 (60)	7 (28)	9 (27)	16 (32)	50 (50)	197	39.4	V
Products are trendy	21 (105)	20 (80)	9 (27)	17 (34)	27 (27)	273	54.6	II

Source: Primary Data

The above table 5.3 shows that majority of the respondents say that the products are of high quality and followed by the trendiness of the product and the professionalism of the sales personnel.

Factors influencing the respondents to prefer a boutique shop

Table 5: Calculation of Garrett Value

Rank	Percent position Value = $100 (R_{ij} - 0.5) / \text{No of rank}$	Garrett value
I	$100 (1 - 0.5) / 5 = 10$	75
II	$100 (2 - 0.5) / 5 = 30$	60
III	$100 (3 - 0.5) / 5 = 50$	50
IV	$100 (4 - 0.5) / 5 = 70$	39
V	$100 (5 - 0.5) / 5 = 90$	25

Source: Primary Data

Table 6: Garrett Ranking

Factors	Score	Average Score	Rank
Attractive advertisements	5108	54.34	IV
Friends and relatives	5452	58	III
Sales personnel	5906	62.82	I
Comfortability	5796	61.65	II
Publicity	4600	48.93	V

Source: Primary Data

Garrett ranking method is used to analyze the factors influencing the respondents towards Boutique shop. The above table 5.4b shows the majority of the respondents are influenced by sales personnel in Boutique shops followed by Comfortability and friends and relatives.

Hypothesis Testing

H₀ 1: There is no association between age and reason for preferring Boutique shop

Age	To look More attractive	To Impress others	To be the first one to introduce the new style	To get the value of money I spend	To get Knowledge About national/ international trend	Total
Below 20 years	3	1	4	2	0	10
21-30 years	0	6	10	2	0	18
31-40 years	5	3	4	8	1	21
41 - 50	8	2	5	10	6	31
51- 60	0	2	3	3	2	10
Above 60	1	0	2	1	0	4
Total	17	14	28	26	9	94

Particulars	Calculated value	Table value at 5%	df	H ₀ accepted/ rejected
Chi- square	36.702	31.4	20	Rejected

Since the calculated value (36.702) is more than the table value (31.4) the hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, there is association between age and their preference towards boutique shops.

H₀ 2: There is no association between frequency of purchase and satisfaction level.

Buying frequency	Excellent	Very good	Good	Satisfied	Total
15 days once	4	1	1	0	6
Monthly once	2	7	4	9	22
Six months once	4	6	5	2	17
Once in a year	3	6	4	12	25
rarely	5	3	10	6	24
Total	18	23	24	29	94

Particulars	Calculated value	Table value at 5%	df	H ₀ accepted/rejected
Chi- square	23.130	21.0	12	Rejected

Since the calculated value (23.130) is more than the table value (21.0) the hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, there is association between frequency of purchase and satisfaction level of the respondents.

Suggestions and Conclusion:

- Awareness must be created among customers so as to increase the purchasing idea in boutique shops.
- Collection of designs must be increased so as to increase a greater number of customers.
- The prices of cloths in boutique are very high when compared to ordinary textile shops.
- There are no collections for the 12 to 16 age group customers. Increasing the collections for those age group customers may result in increased number of sales in boutique

The age wise grouping of customers can be studied in this research. Shopping in boutique is totally different from shopping in ordinary textile shops. It is concluded that limited number of collections are only available in the boutique shops because of unique colors and collections. Most of the customers prefer boutique shops than online boutiques. This study concluded that there is association between age of the customers and their preference towards boutique shop. Further this type of studies can be conducted among men also. Most of the boutique shops are having good image, appealing interior and they are environmental conscious.

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